

JIP06-COVID19-COVRIN-D.4.3.2

Workpackage 4

Responsible Partners:

ANSES (P1), WBVR (P31)

Contributing partners:

ANSES (P1), FLI (P10), BFR (P9), APHA (P21),
ISS (27), IZSAM (P28), ZSLER (P29), WBVR
(P31), PIWET (P34)

GENERAL INFORMATION

European Joint Programme full title	Promoting One Health in Europe through joint actions on foodborne zoonoses, antimicrobial resistance and emerging microbiological hazards
European Joint Programme acronym	One Health EJP
Funding	This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 773830.
Grant Agreement	Grant agreement n° 773830
Start Date	01/01/2018
Duration	60 Months

DOCUMENT MANAGEMENT

Title OHEJP deliverable	D-COVRIN. D4.3.2. Report of pan coronavirus PCR screening, plus next generation sequencing of samples and viral diversity over time.		
WP and task	JIP06-WP2-T4.3 Virus emergence risk modelling/ ST4.3.2 Report of pan coronavirus PCR screening, plus next generation sequencing of samples and viral diversity over time.		
Leader	T4.3 Alessio Lorusso IZSAM (P16), Elodie Monchatre- Leroy ANSES (P1)		
Other contributors	ANSES (P1), FLI (P10), BFR (P9), APHA (P21), ISS (27), IZSAM (P28), IZSLER (P29), WBVR (P31), PIWET (P34)		
Due month of the deliverable	63		
Actual submission month	57		
Type <i>R: Document, report DEC: Websites, patent filings, videos, etc.; OTHER</i>	R, DEC Save date: 30-Mar-23		
Dissemination level <i>PU: Public (default) CO: confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services).</i>	PU		
Dissemination <i>Author's suggestion to inform the following possible interested parties.</i>	OHEJP WP 1 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 2 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 3 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 4 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 5 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 6 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 7 <input type="checkbox"/> Project Management Team <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Communication Team <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Scientific Steering Board <input type="checkbox"/> National Stakeholders/Program Owners Committee <input type="checkbox"/> EFSA <input type="checkbox"/> ECDC <input type="checkbox"/> EEA <input type="checkbox"/> EMA <input type="checkbox"/> FAO <input type="checkbox"/> WHO <input type="checkbox"/> OIE <input type="checkbox"/> Other international stakeholder(s): Social Media: Other recipient(s):		

JIP06-COVID19-COVRIN-D.2.1.1

JIP06-WP4-T4.3 Virus emergence risk modelling

JIP06-WP4 sub-task ST 4.3.2 Report of pan coronavirus PCR screening, plus next generation sequencing of samples and viral diversity over time.

D4.3.2. Report of pan coronavirus PCR screening, plus next generation sequencing of samples and viral diversity over time.

Description of the task

The three main objectives of COVRIN WP4 are:

- 1) Virus-host interaction - to identify possible molecular mechanisms of evolution and host adaptation of coronaviruses
- 2) Drivers of virus emergence - to identify the drivers for virus emergence by highlighting ecological opportunities and human practices that have a direct impact on coronaviruses evolution, in animals and in the vicinity of humans
- 3) Virus emergence risk modelling - research outcomes to the first two of the above objectives will be used to model the risks of virus emergence in different virus-host interaction situations.

This deliverable describes the activities and first outcomes of the **sub-task ST4.3.2** (Report of pan coronavirus PCR screening, plus next generation sequencing of samples and viral diversity over time)

Description of the deliverable

- 1) Detecion of coronaviruses in wildlife

To carry out a pan coronavirus surveillance in animals, 2305 organs and swabs collected from 1629 domestic and wild animals of different species have been analysed from February 2021 to November 2022 by IZSAM. In particular, 768 lungs, 1017 intestines, 39 faeces, 44 rectal/cloacal swabs, 357 nasal/oropharyngeal swabs, 69 brains, 5 lymph nodes, 1 heart, 2 kidneys and 2 spleen belonging to 942 carnivores (115 dogs, 103 cats, 2 wildcats, 60 badgers, 8 martens, 11 weasels, 405 minks, 2 otters, 98 wolves, 97 foxes, 7 bears and 34 dolphins), 196 ruminants (32 bovines, 5 buffaloes, 19 sheep, 8 goats, 100 roe deer, 1 chamois, 1 mouflon and 30 deer), 19 equids (15 horses and 4 donkeys), 120 suids (26 pigs and 94 wild boars), 150 birds (142 wild birds and 8 chickens), 89 rodents (34 rats, 23 mice, 1 nutria, 2 dormice, 1 squirrel and 27 porcupines), 8 hedgehogs, 38 lagomorphs (12 hare and 26 rabbits), 26 bats and 40 snakes have been tested.

All organs were suspended 1:10 p/v in PBS buffer added with antibiotic by using Tissue Lyser (Qiagen) and Nucleic acids have been extracted by using MagMAX™ CORE Nucleic Acid Purification Kit (Applied Biosystems™) and the Thermo Scientific KingFisher Flex automated extractor. Bimolecular analysis has been performed by using a pan coronavirus assay described by Drzewniokova et al. (2021), targeting the viral polymerase. Amplicons obtained from positive samples have been submitted to Sanger sequencing and consensus sequences have been analysed through NCBI database (https://blast.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/Blast.cgi?PROGRAM=blastn&PAGE_TYPE=BlastSearch&LINK_LOC=blasthome).

To date, CoVs infection has been reported in 50 animals (6 dogs, 12 cats, 2 wolves, 5 foxes, 2 bears, 2 minks, 2 badgers, 4 cattle, 3 pigs, 5 hedgehogs, 1 porcupine, 2 bats and 4 mice); detailed results have been reported in table 1.

SPECIES	LUNG	INTESTINE	LUNG + INTESTINE	O.P. SWAB	RECTAL SWAB	FAECES
DOG	1	5				
CAT	2	7	3			
WOLF	1	1				
FOX	2	3				
BEAR	1				1	
MINK				2		
BADGER		2				
BOVINE		2	2			
PIG		3				
HEDGEHOG	1	2				2
PORCUPINE		1				
BAT						2
MOUSE	1	1	2			

Table 1. Positive results obtained from pan coronavirus surveillance in animals.

Sanger sequencing demonstrated the presence of the two most represented CoVs genera among mammals: Alphacoronaviruses and Betacoronaviruses. NGS analysis confirmed these results. All positive cats resulted positive to FCoV, while the wolf lungs showed the presence of CrCoV. Cattle resulted positive to BCoV infection, hedgehogs to Betacoronavirus erinceus, and the porcupine to FCoV. As reported in D1.1.1, a total of 1,036 wildlife samples have been tested for SARS-CoV-2 by APHA and all were negative by E-gene RRT-PCR: fox (n=578), deer (n=92), bats (n=81), bat guano (n=15), mink (n=27), badger (n=184), stoat (n=11), squirrel (n=57) and boar (n=6). Faecal swabs collected from six bats were positive by nested pan CoV RT-PCR and revealed the presence of four alphacoronaviruses (*Pipistrellus pipistrellus*, *Myotis daubentonii*, *Myotis nattereri*) and two betacoronaviruses (*Plecotus auritus*) as reported in ST4.3.1 (APHA P21). Pan CoV PCR has been attempted from tissues collected from GB deer species (Fallow deer n=5, Muntjac deer n=4 and Roe deer n=3) and were negative. Ongoing pan CoV PCR is being continued, supported by Defra, UK programmes: SE0562, SE0567 and SE0569. A case of sudden death in a five-month-old male fallow deer in December 2019 was investigated. Pathological and virological investigations revealed parainfluenza type 3 (PIV-3) to be the primary cause of respiratory disease and death however metagenomic analysis from lung tissue identified co-infection with parainfluenza type 3 (PIV-3) and bovine betacoronavirus (Dastjerdi et al 2022).

2) Detection of coronaviruses in pets

In addition to the pan coronavirus surveillance, samples of dogs cats have been also tested to detect the presence of feline coronavirus. To this aim, IZSAM collected biological samples from 944 cats from 2021 and 2022. Samples preparation and acid nucleic extraction have been performed following the same protocol described above for the pan coronavirus surveillance. Real Time RT-PCR for FIPV has been performed on intestine, lungs, lymph nodes and spleen samples collected from carcasses and on faeces, rectal swabs, whole blood and abdominal ascitic fluid collected from alive cats by using VetMAX™ FIP Dual IPC Kit (Thermo Scientific™). 177/944 cats (18,75%) tested positive. In particular, a total of 16 intestines, 5 lungs, 1 lymph node, 5 spleen of dead cats and 75 fecal samples, 31 rectal swabs, 12 whole blood, 31 abdominal ascitic fluid samples of alive cats tested positive with the adopted molecular test. In 3 cats, FCoV was detected in both lungs and intestine. Positive samples were processed by NGS.

For the same purpose, a total of 3287 serum samples obtained from cats and dogs submitted to APHA as part of the rabies pet travel scheme were tested for SARS-CoV-2 antibodies. Out of these, 54/619 cat serum (8.72%) and 208/2668 dog serum (7.80%) samples tested ELISA positive for SARS-CoV-2 antibodies. In a Defra co-funded study, SE0568, 198 cat serum samples were tested for the presence of feline infectious peritonitis (FIP), a feline coronavirus (FCoV) variant that can be fatal for cats. An ImmunoComb Feline Coronavirus (FCoV) [FIP] Antibody Test Kit (Biogal) was used to determine cat serum IgG antibodies to FCoV. A total of 187/198 (94.4%) cat serum samples were positive for FCoV. This work will be extended and continued via Defra funded projects as part of a collaborative project with the Royal Veterinary College (RVC) whereby 127 corresponding blood clots have been submitted for RNA-Seq which included ten SARS-CoV-2 and FCoV positive samples. These samples will be sequenced to determine host susceptibility to coronavirus in cats at the genomic and transcriptomic level to contribute to our understanding why certain cats/cat breeds are more susceptible to FIP compared to others.

3) NGS analysis

RNAs isolated from two bat guano samples tested positive with pan-coronavirus procedure were subjected for NGS. For RNA isolated from *Myotis daubentonii* mapped to MG923574.2 consensus sequence of 21 382 bp containing several gaps compared to reference sequence was obtained. Phylogenetic analysis revealed the highest nucleotide identity (over 96.0%) to alphacoronaviruses: BtCoV/BatGuano15_SWE2020 isolated in June 2020 in Sweden and Danish alphacoronaviruses identified in 2014 – 2015 (BtCoV/21164-6-alt/M.dau/DK/2015; BtCoV/13585-58/M.dau/DK/2014). For RNA isolated from *Rhinolophus hipposideros* mapping on MW719567.1 consensus sequence of 27 684 bp with few gaps in genome was generated. Phylogenetic analysis performed for the few fragments of CoV isolated from *R. hipposideros* (around 4.5 – 10 kb) revealed a nucleotide identity of 80% to SARS-CoV-2/human/USA/MD-MDH-2632/2021 isolated from human in 2021. Whereas phylogenetic analysis performed for 379 bp of RdRp gene detected with pan-coronavirus procedure and Sanger sequenced revealed the highest relationship to the SLO1A0066/2008/SVN isolate of bat coronavirus obtained in Slovenia from a fecal sample from a horseshoe bat in 2008, to which it had an identity of 96.3–96.5%. FCoV in feline samples were typed as FCoV-I and II and genome analysis unraveling the presence of spike mutations involved in the pathogenic mechanisms driving the enteric viruses into systemic is currently under evaluation.

1. References

Drzewnioková P, Festa F, Panzarin V, Lelli D, Moreno A, Zecchin B, De Benedictis P, Leopardi S. Best Molecular Tools to Investigate Coronavirus Diversity in Mammals: A Comparison. *Viruses*. 2021 Oct 1;13(10):1975. doi: 10.3390/v13101975. PMID: 34696405; PMCID: PMC8538982.

Dastjerdi A, Floyd T, Swinson V, Davies H, Barber A, Wight A. Parainfluenza and corona viruses in a fallow deer (*Dama dama*) with fatal respiratory disease. *Front Vet Sci*. 2022 Dec 6;9:1059681. doi: 10.3389/fvets.2022.1059681.